

**CDB / CARICOM / OECS Model
Learning Recovery and Enhancement
Programme for Caribbean Schools**

Let's REAP!

Overview

<https://lreap.info>

**Organisation of
Eastern Caribbean States**

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All **Let's REAP!** materials are available from all partner organisations: www.caribank.org/letitrip, caricom.org/letitrip and oecs.int/letitrip, as well as at letitrip.info.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

CARICOM	Caribbean Community
CDB	Caribbean Development Bank
COVID-19	Coronavirus disease 2019 caused by SARS-CoV-2
Let's REAP!	Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme (L-R-EA-P)
MoE	Ministry of Education
OECS	Organization of Eastern Caribbean States
OER	Open Educational Resources
SPED	Special education and disability
TPD	Teacher professional development

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

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The COVID-19 pandemic brought significant disruption to the education systems of the member states of the CARICOM, the OECS and other parts of the region, exacerbating existing stresses on the education system. Moreover, the pandemic further widened the education gaps between high-performing and low-performing students, particularly for already disadvantaged learners. Disadvantaged learners include learners of low socio-economic status and those that have special educational needs or a disability (SPED). When the pandemic hit, there were many uncertainties, such as the duration of the pandemic and the impact on teachers, on students, on families and so forth. It is clear that the COVID-19 pandemic has brought significant disruption to the education systems of all countries around the world. In the Caribbean, this has exacerbated the effects of existing stresses and widening education gaps between high-performing and low-performing students, particularly for already disadvantaged learners (such as those with disabilities or from low-income families).

1.1. The Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme

To address the learning loss from unprecedented disruptions in education, the CDB, CARICOM and OECS, commissioned a Learning Recovery and Enhancement Programme, abbreviated as L-R-EA-P and pronounced

Let's REAP!

The focus of **Let's REAP!** is to promote learning improvement in light of the challenges to education brought about by COVID-19. However, the programme also intends to address longer-standing issues which the pandemic has exacerbated, as well as to build the resilience of national education systems to the occurrence of other natural hazards (such as flooding, hurricanes, and volcanic activity) prevalent in the region. **Let's REAP!**, therefore, seeks to

Recover, Improve, Transform

education in the Caribbean.

For **Let's REAP!** to be effective, a multi-pronged approach must be taken, supporting national ministries, principals, and teachers; such a broad approach will set in motion processes that ultimately support learners to improve learning outcomes. In other words, **Let's REAP!** is an intervention for children and young persons, but it is also an intervention for the system around the child: Teachers, principals, parents, community and government.

The implementation of **Let's REAP!** will be driven by principals across OECS and CARICOM. Therefore, there is specific guidance on how to successfully execute the recovery programme is given in this document. This document is primarily aimed at principals, but it is also relevant for other school staff.

Apart from this overview document, accompanying documents for principals ([Let's REAP! — Roadmap for Principals](#)), ministries ([Let's REAP! — Roadmap for Ministries](#)) as well as regional organisations ([Let's REAP! — Roadmap for IGOs](#)) are available. A unique feature of the **Let's REAP!** programme is the coordination across different locations and different areas.

Figure 1. The design of **Let's REAP!**. The programme is designed for systemic integration across four locations (regional, national, schools, community) with nine components of activity.

1.2. The nine components

In brief, the nine components of **Let's REAP!** are:

1. Leadership and accountability;
2. Management and communication;
3. Regional and national partnerships
4. Teacher support and collaboration (school-based TPD and CoPs);
5. Formative assessment;
6. Inclusion, SPED, wellbeing;
7. Resources and curriculum;
8. Engagement with parents and family;
9. Engagement with community and community organisations.

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Figure 2. The nine components (see right of [Figure 1. The design of the LRIP](#)).

1.3. A multi-actor approach

The components work at different levels of organisations. The regional, national and school levels interact to ensure the overall success of the **Let's REAP!**. Importantly, each component is supported by monitoring and evaluation frameworks to ensure accountability at all levels.

Figure 3. Multi-actor cooperation within the programme (see left of *Figure 1. The design of Let's REAP!*).

1. Introduction to Let's REAP!

It is essential for **Let's REAP!** to be as coordinated as possible. This means both 'integration across locations' as well as 'integration within locations'. In other words, **Let's REAP!** needs to be coordinated *between* intergovernmental organisations, national ministries and schools. It also needs to be coordinated *within each of those locations* (e.g., *within schools*).

Figure 4. Integration of the programme within each location.

1.4. Integrating the programme with existing activities

The **Let's REAP!** programme is intended to be a blueprint that can be applied anywhere in the Caribbean. However, this blueprint needs to be tailored to each participating member state. Still, there are common areas that all participating countries need to consider maximising the effectiveness of their interventions. Therefore, it makes sense for the Caribbean intergovernmental organisations (CDB, CARICOM and OECS) to put forward this blueprint: it is a set of resources that supports national agencies to speed up the design and implementation of an effective **Let's REAP!** programme.

In particular, **Let's REAP!** components offer a balanced approach that can address the complexities of learning contexts in the member states, as well as the needs of students and their families, teachers and schools as a whole. Attention must be given to adequate implementation and monitoring to ensure effective performance and execution of **Let's REAP!**, particularly related to the context of the most vulnerable students and their families in each participating member state.

Let's REAP! consolidates a culture of learning that considers country-level needs and priorities, as well as individual learner needs at a classroom level. Nonetheless, recognising that countries and learners in the region may also share some challenges, **Let's REAP!** proposes several core activities that are likely to be implemented across all member states.

Let's REAP! recognises that Caribbean islands are already addressing learning loss brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic. Some focus areas naturally overlap with the ideas in **Let's REAP!**. The **Let's REAP!** programme does not replace those, but integrates with those existing activities.

The following list showcases some ongoing activities.

- In the **Bahamas**, the focus of the recovery programme includes policy adjustments and evidence-based learning recovery. Various kinds of assessments to evaluate learning needs, instruction to respond to needs identified and remediation and accelerated programmes are among some measures taken to address learning gaps. There is also consideration of the production of indigenous resources.
- In **Belize**, the recovery programme focuses on reducing the number of subjects and learning outcomes, administering diagnostic tests, harnessing

education technology to develop a national learning platform and to establish a virtual Teacher Learning Institute to facilitate teacher development, and introduce mechanisms to monitor and support programmes.

- In the **Cayman Islands**, there is an emphasis on psychosocial wellbeing of staff students because there is a recognition that changes to education during the pandemic had a negatively impacted some students. To facilitate psychosocial wellbeing, the programme emphasises that all staff and students are assessed and rehabilitated where necessary. Their recovery also makes allocation for extracurricular activities, TPD and learning loss. To address learning loss and ensure that all areas of the curriculum is covered, differentiated instruction is recommended so that the learning needs of all students are met. Each aspect of the recovery programme is carefully monitored and supported by well-designed frameworks.
- In **Guyana**, there were already issues with learning loss owing to access challenges for students who live in the interior. This situation is exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The recovery programme will focus on diagnostic testing and TPD for formative assessment to ensure that teachers can ascertain where students are academically and adapt teaching to address learning gaps.
- In **St. Lucia**, the priorities for the recovery programme include a curriculum review exploring how to cater for SPED, summer learning programme to address academic gaps, diagnostic assessments, review of parental engagement in ways that empower parents to support more effectively at home and greater access to context relevant resources for education.
- More broadly, **Grenada, Dominica, St. Lucia and St. Vincent and the Grenadines** are implementing a number of actions based on an academic recovery programme initiated through the OECS.

Naturally, there are also recovery efforts undertaken by regional and intergovernmental organisations, including CARICOM, the Caribbean Development Bank, the OECS, UNICEF and the Caribbean Union of Teachers. Alternative assessment strategies, detailed research on learning loss in the region, review of past disasters and their impact on the islands are among some recommendations to address loss of learning across the region.

1.5. The role of evidence: Local and global

The programme proposed here is built on some of the best evidence currently available. It includes feedback, best practices shared and operationalised in CARICOM *Member States*. It also builds on a set of documents developed over a six-month period for the OECS:

- [↑Academic Recovery Programmes in the Eastern Caribbean — Literature Review](#);
- [↑Academic Recovery Programme: Synthesis of Qualitative Data and High-level Overview](#);
- [↑An Academic Recovery Programme for the OECS Member States](#);
- [↑An Academic Recovery Programme for the OECS Member States: Pitch Deck](#);
- [↑Concept Note for the Implementation of the Academic Recovery Programme](#);
- [↑Final Report and Recommendations](#).

The [↑OECS Academic Recovery Programme — Outputs Register](#) contains full details of all outputs produced.

1.6. The strategy is delivery

This concept note and the associated guidance documentation, and offers concrete guidance for implementation. Notably, the materials also suggest indicative timelines and budgets for implementing each **Let's REAP!** component, highlighting critical tasks and responsibilities.

Importantly, the purpose of this strategy is not to have a strategy or a roadmap, but the strategy is delivery (cf. [Greenway, 2018](#)).

“The Strategy is Delivery.”

Greenway (2018)

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